

Determination of Iron and Chromium in Chrome Ores and Refractories by Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry

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An accurate and rapid procedure for determination of Fe and Cr in chrome ores and refractories by fusion with borax-caustic soda followed by Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometric techniques using nitrous oxide acetylene flame has been developed and is reported. The decomposition of the chrome ores and refractories by the fusion mixture of borax-caustic soda has several advantages over the other methods of decomposition. The results obtained with standard samples indicate that the procedure is accurate and precise. The inter-element effect in the proposed method has been overcome by using a matrix solution containing tartaric acid, borax and sodium chloride both in the sample solution and in the standard solution and working in nitrous oxide acetylene flame condition instead of air acetylene flame.

DUE to their highly refractory nature, chromites and chromium bearing refractories cause serious problems in the determination of Fe and Cr by the standard wet chemical method. To achieve accurate results careful manipulation and much experience are required¹⁻⁶.

With the development of the nitrous oxide-acetylene flame the Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometric methods (AAS) are used for the determination of many elements such as Fe, Al, Ti, Ca, Mg, etc. in various materials including silicate rocks, minerals, soils, ores, etc.^{7,8}. But application of AAS to the determination of Fe and Cr in chrome ores and refractories has not been studied widely¹⁰. This is because of the fact that determination of Fe and Cr in chrome ores and refractories depends on two factors i.e. (i) the decomposition of the materials by a suitable flux and preparation of solution and (ii) the establishment of conditions of experiments and instrumental parameters for measurement by AAS without chemical interferences. An investigation was undertaken which has led to the development of a simple and rapid procedure for accurate determination of Fe and Cr in chrome ores and refractories.

The procedure developed is based on the decomposition of the material by fusion with caustic soda-

borate flux in nickel crucible followed by dissolution of the fused mass in hydrochloric acid solution. Appropriate dilute solutions are prepared from the stock solution maintaining a tartaric acid strength to 0.2M, the acid strength to 2N to 3N and sodium ion to about 2000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ in the final volume. The determination of iron and chromium are carried out by aspirating the appropriate dilute solutions in an AA-Spectrophotometer fitted with nitrous oxide-acetylene burner head and digital concentration read out maintaining the instrumental parameters as given in Table-1. The absorption of the resonance line energy from the spectrum of each element has been measured and compared with that from the calibration solution of the same element, maintaining the acid concentrations same as that of the sample solution.

Experimental

1. *Preparation of standard solutions*: (i) Iron (1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$): Prepared from 99.9% purity of iron rod (Spec. pure) by dissolving in minimum quantity of distilled hydrochloric acid.

(ii) Chromium (1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$): Prepared from potassium dichromate (GR, E. Merck) dried at $105 \pm 2^\circ$.

TABLE I

Apparatus :						
Working parameters :						
Instruments : Perkin Elmer 303 model : Double beam Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer equipped with premixing burner (2") and digital concentration reader.						
Element	Source	Wavelength nm	Slit setting	Heating current mA	Flame characteristics	
Fe.	Hollow cathode lamp — Fe.	248.3	3	30	Nitrous oxide-acetylene (rich) with distinct red feathered zone	
Cr.	Hollow cathode lamp — Cr.	357.9	4	30		
Working range : Upto 20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Fe and Cr.						

Preparation of mixed standard of Fe and Cr : Mixed standard of 2,5,10,15 and 20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ are prepared from individual 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Fe and Cr standard stock solutions, sufficient NaCl is added so that the solution had 2000 to 10,000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ Na. Calculated amount of borax and tartaric acid are added to maintain about 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of borax and 0.2M of tartaric acid in the final volume. Calibration curve for Fe and Cr are prepared from these mixed standard.

All other reagents and chemicals used are of GR, E. Merck or AnalaR B.D.H. grade and deionised water is used throughout the experiment.

Procedure : About 0.5g of powdered fused borax was taken in a nickel crucible of 30-35 ml capacity. 0.100g of the sample, powdered to about 200 mesh size was weighed out and properly mixed with borax. 2.5 to 3 g of caustic soda pellets was added and the mixture was warmed on a hot plate in low heat for about an hour to drive out the moisture and then fused carefully over the burner for about 45 min. The crucible with its lid was transferred to a 250 ml beaker containing about 100 ml water. It was warmed on a hot plate till the melt disintegrated completely. The crucible and lid were washed thoroughly first with water, then with about 5 ml of conc. HCl and finally with water, collecting the washings in the beaker. Conc. HCl was added slowly with stirring till the solution was just acidic. About 10 ml more of HCl was added and boiled till the solution was clear. This was cooled to room temperature and transferred to a 200 ml volumetric flask and the volume was made up. A blank solution with all the reagents were prepared following the aforesaid procedure.

An aliquot of 5 ml was transferred into a 50 ml volumetric flask, 5 ml of 2M tartaric acid was added and the volume was made up and mixed well. The dilute sample solution and the blank solution were atomized for absorbance measurement for Fe and Cr in an Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer maintaining the recommended instrumental parameters. The DCR was set to average four readings per sample solution

and the results were calculated from the calibration curve obtained from the standard solutions under similar experimental conditions. The results are recorded in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

Chrome ores and chrome refractories are usually decomposed better by alkaline flux^{1,2,3}. Decomposition by HClO_4 or H_3PO_4 is rather time consuming, sometimes incomplete and not very effective^{1-3,10}. Hence decomposition by an alkaline flux is recommended. The peroxide fusion in nickel crucible is not preferred as, much of nickel ion passes into the solution which interfere in the Atomic Absorption measurement. It has been observed that caustic soda-borate in the ratio of approximately 5 : 1 in nickel crucible decompose smoothly the material powdered to nearly-200 mesh size within an hour and the amount of nickel passing into solution is small and does not interfere in subsequent measurement by Atomic Absorption Spectrometer. The decomposition of the materials is incomplete with a mixture of caustic potash-borate mixture.

The caustic soda-borate fusion mixture has the advantages over other alkaline fluxes in the following respects : (1) low fusion temperature, (2) fusion is complete within an hour, (3) fusion is possible in a nickel crucible and hence the costly platinum crucible is not required, (4) nickel crucible is rarely attacked and as many as about 100 fusions can be carried out with the same crucible, (5) the little amount of nickel that passes into solution does not interfere in the subsequent experiments, (6) analytical grade of the reagents are available comparatively at a cheaper rate and (7) smooth and easy operations suitable for handling a large number of samples.

Numerous interference^{8,9} are reported in the Atomic Absorption determination of Cr in air acetylene flame. The inter-element effects can be overcome by using a matrix solution of tartaric acid (0.1M to 2M) HCl or H_2SO_4 (2N, to 3N), borax (1000 ppm to,

TABLE 2
DETERMINATION OF FE AND CR IN CHROME ORES/REFRACTORIES

Sample	Certificate value	Cr_2O_3^n		FeO*	
		Value by the proposed method	Certificate value	Value by the proposed method	Certificate value
1. BCS No. 308 Grecian chrome ore	41.5	41.30 \pm 0.17 (n=10)	15.30	15.15 \pm 0.052 (n=10)	12.26
2. NBS No. 103A chrome refractory	32.05	32.12	12.40	12.26	12.26
3. IGS 30 chrome refractories (U.K.)	35.04	35.10	14.45	14.35	14.35
4. Chrome ore Orissa (GSI)	60.18**	60.08	10.48**	10.54	10.54
5. Chrome ore Orissa (GSI)	56.48**	56.25	12.50**	12.29	12.29

*Total Fe expressed as FeO.

**Value obtained by conventional wet chemical method^(1,2).

10,000 ppm) and sodium chloride (1000 ppm to 20,000 ppm). Both the sample solution and the standard solution should be prepared accordingly. The use of nitrous oxide acetylene flame also helps to eliminate further the inter-element effects.

The role of tartaric acid is (1) to minimise the inter-element effect, particularly of silicic acid over iron and iron over chromium (2) to reduce Cr^{+6} to Cr^{+3} before atomisation thus maintain one chemical species in the flame (3) to prevent the coagulation of silicic acid and the hydrolysis of titanium, when they are present in the sample at high concentration. Although tartaric acid is tolerated upto 2M strength, it has been observed that about 0.2M strength of tartaric acid is adequate.

Results obtained by the proposed method on standard samples indicate that the method is accurate, reproducible and suitable for routine analysis of chrome ores and refractories for its simplicity, rapidity and easy operations.

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References

1. W. F. HILLBRAND, G. E. P. LUNDELL, H. A. BRIGHT and J. I. HOFFMAN, *Applied Inorganic Analysis*, 2nd Ed., 1955.
2. H. LOW ALBERT, ARTHUR J. WEIMING and WILLIAM, P. SCHODER, *Technical Methods of Ore-Analysis*, 1954.
3. D. E. RYAN, *Analyst*, 1960, 85, 569.
4. I. Z. SARUDI, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1938, 163, 34.
5. J. I. DINNIN, *U.S. Geol. Survey Bull.*, 1959, 1084-B, 31.
6. C. F. VANDER WAL, *J. Analyst*, 1938, 63, 176.
7. J. A. BROWMAN and J. B. WILLIS, *Anal. Chem.*, 1967, 37, 1210.
8. J. MUSIL and M. NEHASIBRA, *Talanta*, 1967, 23, 729.
9. J. MUSIL, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1974, 271, 353.
10. R. P. LUCAS and B. C. RUPRECHT, *Anal. Chem.*, 1971, 43, 1013.